

Standardizing the Mathematical Pronunciation of Natural Numbers: Design Principles and Multilingual Implementation

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Abstract

Current English for 14 is *fourteen* but mathematically it is *ten & four*. Research on number sense, counting, arithmetic and the predictive value for later mathematical abilities tends to be methodologically invalid when it doesn't measure true number sense that can develop when the numbers are pronounced in mathematical proper fashion. Researchers can correct by including proper names in the research design, but this involves some choices, and when each research design adopts a different scheme, also differently across languages, then results become incomparable. A standard would be useful, both ISO for general principles and national implementations. Research may not have the time to wait for such (inter-) national consensus. This article suggests principles of design and implementations for said languages. This can support the awareness about the need for a process towards ISO and national consensus, and in the mean time provides a baseline for research.

Indexed keywords: moderated effects, Google Translate

Article History: Received: 21 January 2019 | Accepted: 14 April 2019 | Published: 24 April 2019

© 2019 The Authors. Open Access under CC BY 4.0. How to cite: Emilia F. Rodriguez, Julian A. Moreno (2019). Standardizing the Mathematical Pronunciation of Natural Numbers: Design Principles and Multilingual Implementation. Journal of Computer Engineering, 8(4), 1–10. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.193045>
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Introduction

There is the distinction between (1) a mathematical pronunciation of the natural numbers (0, 1, 2, 3, ...) and (2) the pronunciation of those numbers in the natural languages (English, German, ..., French). While we will use the term "natural language" those languages clearly have been subjected to changes by influential authors and often even committees. Thus the present discussion on a standard on mathematical pronunciation is no breach upon nature itself.

Subsequently we observe that the distinction between (1) and (2) hinders research on number sense, counting and arithmetic, and their predictive value for later mathematical competence. Research methods may suffer from methodological invalidity when they mistake "number sense in natural language" for "true number sense with mathematical pronunciation". Researchers can try to correct by providing pupils with mathematical names, as Ejersbo & Misfeldt (2015) do. There is a risk that researchers implement their own interpretation of what mathematical names are, so that comparison of results becomes more and more difficult or impossible. Hence, a (golden) standard for such mathematical pronunciation will be useful, for achieving both validity and comparability.

For such a standard, we first establish the need, then propose principles of design, and then implement those principles to generate proposals for English, German, French, Dutch and Danish. It must be hoped that there will be a process towards consensus on such standards, both in ISO manner and national implementation. This article hopes to generate interest for such a process. In the mean time, researchers who are already in need of a baseline might be helped by the present suggestions.

The present issue differs principally from spelling reform. The spelling of a number ("29"), remains the same. Only its pronunciation changes. The new pronunciation will be spelled in common fashion too. This issue is not about spelling but about bilingualism and mathematical ability. A discussion in the media is by Shellenbarger (2014) in the WSJ.

The need for a standard

Professor Fred Schuh of TU Delft in 1943 observed that the Dutch pronunciation of the numbers was awkward. While English has *twenty-seven* in the order of written 27, Dutch has *zeven-en-twintig*. He again discussed this in Schuh (1949) and formulated a proposal for change, focussing on the numbers above 20. The proposal reached the Dutch minister of education, see Stoffels (1952), but it was not adopted.

Researchers in Norway had observed the same problem, and the Norse parliament (Storting) adopted a change in 1950, which we see reflected in the pronunciation after 1951.

¹ I am not aware of an evaluation report. ² Pixner et al. (2011) observe that the Czech language allows both kinds of pronunciation, and they show that the mathematical order causes less errors than the inverted order.

Various authors look into number sense, counting and arithmetic, in which there is an interplay of language, embodiment (fingers), nonsymbolic forms (e.g. dots), symbols

(Indian-Arabic numbers), and working memory. Dowker & Roberts (2015) and Mark & Dowker (2015) compare English, Welsh and Cantonese. Zuber et al. (2009), Moeller et al (2011), Klein et al. (2013) indicate that inversion in German slows down the learning progress w.r.t. mathematics proper. In Holland, Friso - Van den Bos (2014), XenidouDervou (2015) and Xenidou-Dervou et al. (2015) indicate the same for Dutch.

Hopefully this research generates interest amongst policy makers to adopt changes like in Norway 1950/51. However, such changes may still be limited w.r.t. a full mathematical pronunciation. Also English isn't perfect. It would be better to have *ten & one* for 11 and *two-ten & one* for 21. Thus the challenge is larger, also for English and Norse.

Recent studies that compare the performances in languages suffer from the problem that they may study the obvious. Schuh (1949) didn't need modern statistics to arrive at the logical conclusion that number-names are better pronounced as they are written. The real problem lies in the policy making process, see Colignatus (2015ab).

The research on the development of number sense tends to suffer from methodological invalidity. In truth, number sense is defined with the use of mathematical pronunciation. The reason for this is that numbers themselves are defined as such. A natural language tends to be a dialect of the mathematical pronunciation. One should not take a dialect as the norm. Studies that do not allow children to develop number sense by using the mathematical names, will not observe true number sense, but "number sense in natural language". It may be admitted that one can develop statistical measures on such observations, but such a result is an awkward construct of both true number sense and confusion in language, in unclear mixture, without scientific relevance. ³

The research on the development of number sense will also benefit from when researchers have deeper roots in mathematics education research (MER). The research quoted above derives mainly from the realm of (neuro-) psychology, and the problems on relevance, validity and comparability might have been observed at an earlier stage when there had been more awareness about what it actually is that pupils must learn. For a mathematician as Fred Schuh the pronunciation *zeven-en-twintig* is obviously illogical, while a neuro-psychologist may record it statistically as an "inversion", and actually think that this is how numbers are pronounced also mathematically, given that mathematicians also use such names. When (neuro-) psychologists would look deeper into MER, they must be warned that this field is not without problems of its own, however. See Colignatus (2015ab) for a longer discussion.

Relevant for research is the question whether pupils can deal with the difference between mathematical names and natural language dialect names. We see that many children can manage, see the examples of Czech, bilingual Chinese, bilingual English & X (e.g. in Holland), and in Ejersbo & Misfeldt (2015). The problem is not with children but in the policy making process, see Colignatus (2015a, 2018b).

Thus, researchers interested in number sense, validity and relevance, will tend to follow the example by Ejersbo & Misfeldt (2015) and include in the research design an instruction for pupils for using mathematical names. Perhaps researchers can find schools that are willing to participate in experiments with dual names, given that these aren't really

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much of experiments since we know that most children can deal with it. When parents are properly informed and first receive a training in the mathematical names, they might readily sign consent forms.

Colignatus (2015a, 2018b) contains a chapter *Marcus learns counting and arithmetic with ten*. This text contains a stylized presentation for six-year olds. This is not intended for actual use in class but contains the framework for starting to think about that. There are translations for German, French, Danish and Dutch, that is: at this moment of writing the text still is in English but the numbers have been replaced by those in the **Appendix** below. This can also be used to instruct parents.

The real bottleneck then becomes comparability of research results. There are still questions of design. Different researchers might use different rules, and thus we would lose comparability. This establishes the need for a standard.

Principles of design

It is easy to suggest a "mathematical pronunciation of numbers in German", but what would that be ? When we use current *zehn* for 10, then there arises a problem, since the present pronunciation of 19 could be the mathematical pronunciation of 90. This will generate great confusion, and Germans would have to check continuously whether others are using current or mathematical names. However, German might replace *zehn* by *zig* or adopt English *ten* or scientific *deca* (though two syllables).

<i>Number</i>	<i>Math in English</i>	<i>English</i>	<i>Math in German ?</i>	<i>German</i>	<i>Math in German</i>
19	ten & nine	nineteen	zehn & neun	neunzehn	zig & neun
90	nine-ten	ninety	neun-zehn	neunzig	neun-zig

proposed principles of design are:

- (1) Pronunciation fully follows the place value system ... $c \times \text{hundred} + b \times \text{ten} + a = \dots cba$. The current convention to start with the digit with the highest place value is fine. (See Colignatus (2015a, 2018b) for lesser alternatives in pronunciation and order.) Much of arithmetic can be done by proper pronunciation (e.g. $2 \times 10 + 4 = 24$).
- (2) In writing out the pronunciation, also in educational texts, the connectives middle-dot(unpronounced) and ampersand (pronounced) are used. We thus say *five-ten* & *nine* for 59, where the dot is not pronounced and the order helps to decode the position. The middle dot is preferred over the hyphen since the latter may be confused with the minus-sign. ⁴
- (3) **Insert August 20 2018:** (3a) For everyday use (in school) there is simplification in the pronunciation of 1 and 0. The proposed standard has simplified 11 = "ten & one" and not the nonsimplified "one-ten & one-one". (3b) On occasion the nonsimplified form can be used. A teaching objective is that pupils should understand the positional system, and the nonsimplified pronunciation indeed is more informative on this than the simplified pronunciation. However, while the nonsimplified form must be shown for such purpose, the everyday use is served by the simplified form. See Colignatus (2018a) for software that can show both forms, with default simplification. See below for more discussion of this aspect in education.

- (4) There is awareness of the distinction between the process of calculation and the result given by the number. The process would be *two times ten plus four* and the result would be *two-ten & four*. On occasion *two of ten and four* might have the double role of both process and result. Operators might be bracketed or coloured to indicate that they are not pronounced, as in *two (times) ten plus four*. It must be tested whether young children would be served by a phase in which those operators are still pronounced also for the number result. Also elder pupils might at occasion be reminded of it. Also other names than times must be researched (e.g. the verb *to of*). Plus and minus however would be universal (given that "and" might not be commutative, as in *he missed the train and arrived late at work*).
- (5) There are no exceptions in pronunciation of the digits in different place value positions. For example, German currently uses *sieben* in 7 and 27 and *sieb* in 70. A choice must be made for one name only. As a rule the shortest name is selected. For English some authors use *tens* as in *two-tens & one*, but *ten* is the value of the place, and must be used consistently. Multiplication can be scalar multiples (2 km) or consists of making groups, and can be expressed by the word *times*, or find another word that expresses this better, such as *grouping*.
- (6) A key point for the standard is that it is identified where languages can make choices. Thus, a proposal for German identifies such a choice between *zig* and *ten*. It is up to German what it selects, but the standard helps German identify the choice.
- (7) If the name of 10 cannot be used as a base (e.g. German *zehn* and Dutch *tien*) then it is tried to find a close substitute already in use (e.g. *zig* in German and *tig* in Dutch), while often a clear option is to use English *ten* or scientific *deca*.
- (8) The above only gives the cardinals. There are also the ordinals (first, second, third,...) and the fractions (that abuse the ordinals, e.g. "a fifth"). The fractions are solved by using $y x^H = y / x = "y \text{ per } x"$ ($H = -1$). The ordinals are solved by adopting a single extension, e.g. English "th" (one-th, two-th, three-th, ...) or Dutch "de" (een-de, tweede, drie-de, ...). There is no linguistic morphing (Dutch *tig-de* doesn't become *tig-ste*).
 - 5 Colloquial words like English *first* and French *premier* will gradually adopt a meaning of "*to begin with*" rather than an ordinal number.
- (9) The rule is that mathematical names are used *in calculation*. The national natural language is explained as a dialect of mathematics. It is an explicit educational goal to identify the national language as such a dialect.
- (10) It will be useful to denote mathematical pronunciation with a label, say *English-M* and *Deutsch-M*. This now holds for numbers but this may apply to more phenomena later on, notably for the vocabulary. This suits translations too, e.g. Google Translate.
- (11) These principles are targeted at becoming a consensus ISO standard. Countries define their own mathematical pronunciation based upon such a standard, and include own national improvements. For example, 7 in Dutch is consistently *zeven* in 7, 27 and 70, but when Dutch changes, it might opt for a single syllable *zeef* anyway. English might prefer *thir* over *three*, with *thirteen*, *thirty* and *third* then becoming *ten & thir*, *thir-ten*

and *thir-th*. (This choice though is not likely, because of potential confusion between *thir-ten* and *thirteen*.)

A suggestion is to have an expert meeting on this. In the mean time it still seems wise to provide this paper that identifies the issue. While the proposals in this paper may already be used in research to enhance comparability, ISO & national standards would be needed for further use such as in official education requirements (US Common Core) and eventually national adoption also in courts of justice.

Amendment May 14 2018

Colignatus (2018a) (update today or later) provides software in *Mathematica* to show how it all would hear and look, taking advantage of the modern facilities for sounds and translation. Revisiting the issue causes the following amendments.

(1) The symbol \mathcal{D} (capital eth) can be used as symbolic 10, and be pronounced as “deka”. The number 10 is universal already, but when each language pronounces it differently, then the universal pronunciation of $\mathcal{D} = 10 = \text{deka}$ may help at times. For example, \mathcal{D}^0 , \mathcal{D}^1 , \mathcal{D}^2 , \mathcal{D}^3 , ... indicates the place values and does not invite to do an actual calculation.

(2) It is better to use the (smaller) ampersand (&) to separate the place value positions. This is used above but is a major revision of the earlier text of 2015 and deserves clarification. Thus also for higher positions as e.g. $657 = \text{six-hundred \& five-ten \& seven}$.

⁵ See the importance of the ordinals for developing number sense (a chapter in Colignatus (2015a, 2018b)): <https://boycottholland.wordpress.com/2014/08/01/is-zero-an-ordinal-or-cardinal-number-q/>

The connectives "&" and "." have an important role in the pronunciation and writing of the words of the numbers. They differ from the mathematical operators "plus" and "group" (multi-plus), since + and \times have commutation, association and distribution.

- The ampersand (&) is the ghost of addition, but simply "and", and not as the operator "plus" with all its properties. The ampersand should be pronounced to separate the place value positions. It is already (often) pronounced in German, Dutch and Danish, and other languages better adopt this practice too. It may take some time to get used to this but afterwards you will wonder why you never did before.
- The center dot (not pronounced) is the ghost of multiplication of the weight and the place value. It is not pure multiplication, like 5 days 2 hamburgers is not quite the same as 2 days 5 hamburgers.

Kids in kindergarten and Grade 1 live in a world of sounds. Thus it is important to also provide them with the &-separator of the place value positions, so that they have this anchor to distinguish which from what. For adults and native speakers of English it may seem superfluous. Indeed, I myself in (2015a, footnote 10, and also the former version of this proposal for a standard) found the use of "&" "distractive", and proposed to use the center dot for "&" too: thus as $25 = \text{two-ten-five}$, without the distinction and merely as an unpronounced connective,. However, after much consideration, the empirical observation is that the &-separator really is there. Its existence must be acknowledged instead of hidden from sight.

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Namely, in natural language, putting two terms alongside, like in 2 km, means a scalar multiplication. In multiplication as grouping, kids learn to use the times-symbol, but you do not use it for 2 km, like 2×1 km. Later students will learn that $2a$ is multiplication in general, also dropping the times-symbol. If they would have been trained by the pronunciation of the very numbers (and this a would be a number, in this scenario like in $a = 25 = \text{two}\cdot\text{ten}\cdot\text{five}$, thus without the "&") then we create a conundrum: (i) within " $a = 25 = \text{two}\cdot\text{ten}\cdot\text{five}$ " the lack of an interfix means addition and (ii) outside of this, in $2a$, the lack of an interfix means multiplication? We should not create conundrums. Thus $25 = \text{two}\cdot\text{ten} \& \text{five}$.

Indeed, in kindergarten and Grade 1 kids will tend to focus on the & as an important new symbol in their universe, but this is not "distractive" but only fortunate, because it will form a stepping stone for the later learning on addition, i.e. using plus. Eventually they would tend to focus on the figures in the numbers and not the connectives.

Addendum June 28 2018. (i) New findings Van der Ven et al. (2017) and Bussi et al. (eds) (2018) have not been included here but may be mentioned. (ii) I discovered that there is the use of "tigus" (proto-Germanic) and "tigjus" (Gothic) for 10s (more sources). (iii) This suggestion to achieve a standard finds support at <https://zwanzigeins.jetzt>

Addendum September 14 2018: Hyphens used in common terms like *twenty-one*.

Implementation

The implementation of these principles of design to English, German, French, Dutch and Danish results in the proposals in the **Appendix**. (They are also used in *Marcus learns counting and arithmetic with ten* in Colignatus (2015a, 2018b) and its online translations.)

For English, German, Dutch and Danish we skip the elaboration of the numbers 50-100 since these follow the system from 20-50.

For French, the numbers for 70-99 are fully written out however. This again shows the difficulty of international comparisons.

Addendum August 20 2018. The pronunciation in the natural language is called "partial" with respect to the place value system. Education and research are better served with the full pronunciation. Colignatus (2018a) shows (also with software) how the full pronunciation has a basic nonsimplified form while everyday use is better served with simplification.

See above point (3) on teaching of the place value system and simplification. There are (3a) the standard for everyday use (in school) with simplification, and (3b) the question how to teach the positional system and the proposed standard with simplification. This teaching might need its own standard too. However, didactics would require more research. Thus the following considerations are preliminary:

- (1) The proposed standard for everyday use has simplification. It is more natural to pronounce 9 as "nine" instead of "nine-one".
- (2) It is most sensible to start from day 1 in kindergarten with using the proposed standard with the simplified pronunciation. This is what the pupils must learn. It would be problematic to first learn the nonsimplified form and later unlearn it again.

- (3) The nonsimplified pronunciation must occur at least sometimes during education, to clarify to pupils how the positional system works, and to clarify the role of zero.
- (4) Researchers who have wondered about the basic or the simplified form as a standard, better see this as an issue in didactics. There is no need for uncertainty about what the standard for everyday use should be. There is only the empirical question about the didactics of (4a) the place value system and (4b) its simplification in pronunciation. (I thank Peter Morfeld of Zwanzigeins for a discussion on this.)

A suggestion for the didactics is as follows. Suppose that a bike has an odometer (distance meter) and that the display changes as in below table (imagine the digit-wheels turning). The pure pronunciation clearly shows the positional values and their weights. This allows pupils to get to understand how this system works and why zero is so important. A principle is that leading zero's are not pronounced, so that 9 is nine-one without simplification but 109 would give one.hundred & zero-ten & nine-one.

<i>Last two digits in an odometer</i>	<i>Nonsimplified pronunciation</i>	<i>Simplified</i>
...09	(zero·ten &) nine·one	nine
...10	one·ten & zero·one	ten
...11	one·ten & one·one	ten & one

Conclusions

The mathematical pronunciation of numbers is straightforward. The only bottleneck is consensus, as language tends to be a social phenomenon. (It remains amazing that two people who haven't met before appear able to speak the same language.)

The principles of design are based upon the place value system, full adherence, minimal distance from current natural language, and a preference for short words. The principles allow the identification of choices to be made.

A prospective implementation is useful, firstly as an example of what it all might mean, secondly to provide researchers, who cannot wait for (inter-) national consensus to continue with their research goals, with a baseline suggestion. Both aspects would support the process towards such ISO & national results.

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PM 1. Colignatus is the name of Thomas Cool in science.

PM 2. References in footnotes need not be repeated here.

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